

Copper Complexes of vic-oxime-imines

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Manuscript received 24 September 1973 ; accepted 29 July 1974

Copper complexes Cu(L)Cl_n have been prepared where LH represents vic-imine-oxime (I). Magnetic susceptibility and electrical conductivity of some of them were determined and used in discussing their structures.

IN continuation of our studies on glyoxime-type N-ligands^{1,3} and their transition metal complexes^{4,5}, we now present our studies on the copper complexes of vic-oxime-imines (I). Pfeiffer⁶, Brady and Muers⁷ and Thilo and Friedrich⁸ found that monoethers and monoimino and mono methyl imino compounds(II) from complexes in the same manner as vic-dioximes. We found that even though nickel complexes of vic-dioximes were diamagnetic, those of the corresponding vic-oxime-(aryl) imines were paramagnetic.

The copper complexes, obtained in the present studies, can be represented as Cu(L)Cl_n (III) where LH is the oxime-imine (I) and $n=1$ or 2. The results indicate that the displacement of chlorine from copper chloride by the ligand is partial only. Such partial displacement of chlorine from copper chloride has not been observed by us with the dioximes related to oxime-imines (I). It can be attributed, in the first instance, to the steric effect of the aryl group attached to the imino group hindering the formation of square planar complexes (CuL_2). Further, the formation of additional rings by hydrogen-bonding ($=\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{H}\dots\text{O}-\text{N}=\text{}$) is well established in the metal complexes of glyoximes ; such rings and hydrogen-bonds will be absent in the metal complexes of oxime-(substituted) imines.

The magnetic moment of these complexes is found to be 1.88 to 1.95 B.M. at room temperature. The results indicate square planar ligand field around copper.

The molar electrical conductivity of these complexes is found to be 5 to 10 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$ in alcoholic solution. It indicates non-electrolytic nature of the complex. Hence the complex is considered to be binuclear, involving chlorine bridges as

These complexes are soluble in organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, etc. providing further indication of non-ionic nature of the complex. The chlorine bridges, however, do not assist in spin-spin interaction of bridged metal atoms.

Experimental :

Schiff bases from N-aryl 2,3-dioxo butyramide 2-otme : These Schiff bases (Ia, Ib, Ic) were prepared as reported earlier.

Schiff base from 2,3-butane dione 2-oxime and p-phenetieine : It was prepared by the above method. It was obtained as pale yellow crystals melting at 166°C. (Analysis : Found : %N : 12.40 ; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires %N : 12.72).

Copper complexes :

When the schiff base (I) (0.003 mole) in alcohol was mixed with aqueous solution of copper chloride (0.001 mole) brown green precipitates were obtained. These were digested on water bath for about an hour, filtered, washed with water and dil. alcohol and dried. The product was recrystallised from benzene+petroleum ether. M. P., analysis, etc. of these complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes are soluble in alcohol, acetone, dioxane, benzene, ether, etc. and sparingly soluble in water and petroleum ether.

The magnetic susceptibility (χ_g) of these complexes was determined on Gouy's magnetic balance at room temperature. The magnetic moment of the complexes studied is presented in Table 1.

The electrical conductivity of these complexes was determined in alcoholic solution by the conductivity bridge method. The molar conductivity of the complexes studied is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COPPER COMPLEXES OF OXIME-IMINES (I)

No.	Oxime imine.	Formula of the complex.	M.P. °C.	% Analysis				Magnetic moment B.M.	Molar Conductivity cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
				Cu found.	N found.	Cu reqd.	N. reqd.		
1.	I-a	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₄ Cl Cu	158	15.20	10.30	15.33	10.12	1.88	5
2.	I-b	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₄ Cl Cu.	172-74	15.20	10.39	15.45	10.22	1.95	10
3.	I-c	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₄ Cl Cu.	160	15.17	9.90	14.80	9.79		
4.	I-d	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl Cu.	150	17.50	8.07	17.94	7.90		

Acknowledgement

We express our thanks to Prof. S. M. Sethna for his keen interest in the work and for providing laboratory facilities and to Dr. S. S. Lele for the microanalysis of the samples.

References

1. A. M. TALATI and T. I. PATEL., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 602 ;
2. A. M. TALATI and P. M. DESAI., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 677 ;
3. A. M. TALATI and T. I. PATEL., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 205 ;
4. A. M. TALATI and T. I. PATEL., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 667 ;
5. A. M. TALATI and R. N. KAPADIA., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 346 ;
6. P. PFEIFFER., *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1811.
7. O. L. BRADY and M. M. MUERS., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1599 ;
8. E. THILO and K. FRIEDRICH., *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 2990 ;